

Acceleration plan Educational innovation with ICT

Maturity-Model

EdTech tools are only used in teaching when tools clearly add value to didactics. Teaching staff is aware of didactical value added.	There are processes and strategy to implement proven EdTech experiments that add value to educational work. EdTech competencies are being researched.	A function is created and dedicated to EdTech and innovation processes.	EdTech portfolio is interoperable and does not rely solely on LMS integration.
Support teams and Educators work together to understand EdTech Needs of Educators.	There are clear guidelines of how to coordinate departments for experimentation.	University has begun to organize a network day(s) to welcome the startups into an ecosystem. EdTech strategy is aligned to mission and vision of university.	There is a standardized architecture available to EdTech vendors to develop from.
Staff is capable of safely experimenting with EdTech Tools.	Procurement and exit strategies of EdTech tools are successfully implemented.	EdTech Strategy is prepared. No connection to mission or vision of University.	An inventory of EdTech tools is available.
Staff are incapable of experimenting with EdTech.	There are no running EdTech experiments.	There are no experimentation environments available for EdTech.	There is no strategy regarding EdTech curation and experimentation.
People	Structure	Strategy	Systems

Subdimensions

Culture	Processes	Vision	Interoperability
Leadership	Procurement	Ownership	EdTech Inventory
Community	Agility	Steering	Standardization & Architecture
Competencies		Budget	Security / Privacy
Behaviour		Decision Making	Data Management
		Responsibility	Experimentation Environment